

**NOVEL OF EDUCATION (BILDUNGSROMAN): HISTORY OF
DEVELOPMENT AND PECULIARITIES**

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Abstract: The theme of the novel of education, also known as Bildungsroman, has a rich history of development and peculiarities that have shaped the genre over time. This abstract aims to provide an overview of the theme's history and highlight its distinctive characteristics.

Key words: Microenvironment, macroenvironment, approach, novel, education, genre, transformation, heteroglossia, image

Introduction. The educational novel, or as it is called in literature Bildungsroman, is a fairly common literary genre. Mainly, such works show readers the problems of moral, psychological and social formation of a person's personality. "The Novel of Education or Educational Novel (French: Roman d'apprentissage, Roman d'éducation; German: Bildungsroman) is a type of novel that became widespread in the literature of the German Enlightenment. Its content is the psychological, moral and social formation of the personality of the protagonist."

The analytical approach to the study of the modern novel is a triad: personality (protagonist) - microenvironment - macroenvironment, where, accordingly, the concept of "macroenvironment" includes time, place of events, aesthetic-moral, political state of society and more.

It seems to us that the main components of the analysis of the literary text of a novel are, first of all, the personality, its inner world, the role of the microenvironment and macroenvironment in its development.

Materials and methods. Of all types of novels of formation, M.Bakhtin singles out a novel in which “the formation of man is given in continuous connection with historical formation.” “The very concept of the world as an experience, as a school in the novel of education was very productive” (Bakhtin, 1986: 214). In the realistic type of novel of education, according to M.Bakhtin, a person “becomes together with the world, reflects in himself the historical formation of the world itself... It is precisely the foundations of the world that change, and a person has to change with them” (Bakhtin, 1986: 214). As if in opposition to M.Bakhtin, E.Vodolazkin created his own concept of the novel of education, arguing that a person should not change for the worse, even if the world has changed for the worse. In this context, in our opinion, “Aviator” by E.Vodolazkin and “Text” by D.Glukhovsky, two novels about crime and repentance, deserve special attention. These works of the 2010s will still survive different levels of perception, interpretation of content, interpretation of meanings and main images. We offer our version of reading two novels, based on an analytical approach: personality, microenvironment, macroenvironment.

The appeal to the novel of education as one of the varieties of the novel genre is largely explained by the fact that the problem of the genre, and in particular the genre of the novel, remains one of the pressing problems of domestic and foreign literary criticism. This is evidenced by the appearance in recent years of a large number of works devoted to the study of the novel. Among them are “The French historical novel of the first half of the 19th century: the evolution of the genre” (1999) by N. A. Litvinenko, “Russian classic novel of the 19th century. Problems of poetics and typology of the genre” (1997) N.D. Tamarchenko, "Gothic novel in Russia" (2002) V. Vatsuro, "A novel about an artist as a “novel of creation.” Genesis and Poetics" (2000) N. S. Bochkareva and others.

N. A. Litvinenko’s approach to the study of the problem of genre seems productive. In particular, in the work “The French Historical Novel of the First Half of the 19th Century: Evolution of the Genre” N. A. Litvinenko points out that “the types of modifications and their diversity give reason to talk about the structural

transformation of the theme as a mode of the genre,” therefore “it is important not to absolutize any one invariant of the genre, one modification, but to comprehend the specifics of the transformation of the thematic principle, acquiring or losing one or another genre function.”

Results and discussion. A classic novel of education can be defined as a novel about the formation of a hero in its diversity and complexity, showing the gradual evolution of the image; it reveals the dialectic of the formation of the hero’s spiritual world, draws attention to such psychological structures as self-denial and self-overcoming, the birth of a new consciousness during the struggle, shows confrontation ideas, mutually exclusive states. In the literature of the 20th century, the type of hero of the educational novel is changing: the hero-truth-seeker becomes a hero-probationer; this genre is no longer characterized by the psychologization of the image, detailed introspection, and thinking in the paradigm of good and evil. The hero of a 20th-century coming-of-age novel is an unusual child, he is “careless, worthless” (Holden Caulfield, J.D. Salinger’s “The Catcher in the Rye”) or, on the contrary, gifted, possessing unusual, sometimes frightening abilities (Frank Coldheim, I. Banks "The Wasp Factory"). Ralph (W. Golding “Lord of the Flies”) also immediately stands out for his ability to think, make decisions, and desire to take responsibility. “Ralph was so calm, and still tall, and he had such a good face... he was, of course, not like the others.

The main idea of the classic novel of education is the birth and formation of a dynamic personality; in the novel of education of the 20th century, the manifestation of this personality in action is important. In classical literature, we see the hero from the first minutes of his life, we know his backstory, all this explains the features of his character and the reasons for his actions; in a novel about the coming of age of a new type, we see a hero at a decisive moment, we do not know the history of his development, or we know it from the point of view from the perspective of the hero himself, we see his inner view of what is happening.

The works of M. M. Bakhtin made a great contribution to the study of the novel. M. Bakhtin considers the most important features of the novel to be its

“unpreparedness” and “incompleteness,” which precisely imply the readiness of the genre for further development and transformation. If we take its linguistic aspect, the novel appears as “artistically organized social heteroglossia, sometimes heteroglossia, and individual heterophony,” which together create a special “higher unity” and give this genre dialectical integrity. At the same time, according to the scientist, “the most outwardly visual and at the same time historically very significant form of introducing and organizing heteroglossia is provided by the so-called humorous novel, the classic representatives of which in England were Fielding, Smollett, Stern, Dickens, Thackeray.” And then M. Bakhtin gives an example of an analysis of such heteroglossia using the example of excerpts from Charles Dickens’s novel “Little Dorrit”, which shows the skill of a writer who knows how to play “a varied game with the boundaries of speeches, languages and horizons.” This art of novelistic prose was also evident in the writer’s early novels, including the novel “The Life and Adventures of Nicholas Nickleby.”

As for the relationship of the novel with other genres, M. Bakhtin distinguishes two aspects of this problem, which can conventionally be called “internal” and “external”. On the one hand, the scientist sees that the novel is “omnivorous”; it readily includes elements of any other genre, literary or “non-fiction” (the latter include church sermons, diaries, legal documents, etc.). A novel can just as easily parody these other genres. On the other hand, according to the scientist, the novel “does not fit well with other genres. He fights for his dominance in literature, and where he wins, other, old genres decay.” Starting from the twentieth century, the novel has become increasingly diversified in form and thematically - forms such as the “river novel”, which includes large novel cycles, a novel consisting of a chain of short stories, a novel-film script, etc. have emerged. The branch of science fiction literature is expanding, including prediction novels, dystopias, and “space operas.” A “fantasy” novel emerges, combining novel intrigue with elements of fairy tales, legends, and mystical literature. Any genre, on the one hand, is always individual, on the other, it is always based on literary tradition. The genre category is a historical category: each era is characterized

not only by a genre system as a whole, but also by genre modifications or variations in particular in relation to a particular genre. Today, literary scholars distinguish varieties of the genre on the basis of a set of stable properties (for example, the general nature of the theme, properties of imagery, type of composition, etc.). Conventionally, the typology of the novel can be represented as follows:

- The themes differ from autobiographical, documentary, political, social; novel of education, philosophical, intellectual; female, family and household; historical; adventurous, fantastic; satirical; sentimental, etc.

- according to structural characteristics: a novel in verse, a travel novel, a pamphlet novel, a parable novel, a feuilleton novel, etc. Often the definition correlates a novel with the era in which one or another type of novel dominated: ancient, knightly, educational, Victorian, gothic, modernist, etc.

In addition, the epic novel stands out - a work in which the center of artistic attention is the fate of the people, and not the individual. Like any genre, a novel must have specific features. M. M. Bakhtin, who identifies three main features of the genre model of the novel, which fundamentally distinguish it from other genres:

- the stylistic three-dimensionality of the novel, associated with the multilingual consciousness realized in it;
 - radical change in the time coordinates of the literary image;
 - a new zone for constructing a literary image, namely the zone of maximum contact with the present (modernity) in its incompleteness.

To summarize this brief review, the novel can be defined as the most universal genre formation, especially adapted to any artistic transformations, to interaction with any types of texts, both oral (mythology, folklore) and written (poetry, drama, scientific texts, business documents etc.).

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